

Resorption in Endodontics II

Dr. Rajiv K. Chugh

National President, Indian Dental Association
Member, Dental Council of India
Secretary General, Indian Academy of Restorative Dentistry
Editor-in-Chief (Asia), UPDENT- A Journal of Advanced Dentistry
Vice Chairman, Pierre Fauchard Academy, India Section

Internal Root Resorption

Internal inflammatory and internal replacement root resorption

Internal root resorption is initiated along the root canal wall and may result in the progressive destruction of the adjacent radicular dentine. IRR may consist of granulation tissue only (inflammatory internal root resorption) or a combination of granulation and bone-like tissue (replacement internal root resorption).

Clinical Features

Internal inflammatory and internal replacement types of IRR share similar clinical features. Teeth with IRR are often asymptomatic and detected as an incidental radiographic finding.

The symptoms and signs of acute or chronic pulpitis, if present, depend on the pulp status, the degree of hard tissue destruction and the position of the resorption in the tooth. The affected tooth with partially vital pulp tissue may be contaminated by bacteria and elicit symptoms and/or signs of acute pulpitis. In established IRR cases, the pulpal tissue may become necrotic and chronically infected resulting in symptoms and/or signs of acute or chronic apical periodontitis. Therefore, patients may present with an abscess or sinus, tenderness to percussion and/or discolouration. IRR in the coronal third of the root canal may present with a pink discolouration in the crown of the tooth due to resorption and replacement of the hard tissue by fibrovascular granulomatous tissue. This pink discolouration of the crown may also be misdiagnosed as external cervical resorption (ECR).

Radiographic Features

IRR may occur anywhere within the root canal system. Internal inflammatory root resorption typically presents as a symmetrical oval- or circular-shaped extension of the root canal (ballooning) radiolucency. Internal replacement root resorption usually presents as an irregularly shaped radiolucency with a mottled or clouded appearance due to bone-like tissue deposits around the borders and within the resorptive defect.

It is well established that ECR and IRR share similar radiographic features on (2-dimensional) radiographs and can be indistinguishable from each other resulting in misdiagnosis. The parallax radiographic technique may be used to help confirm the nature of the resorption; the IRR defect will not change position in relation to the root canal; however, ECR will move in the same or opposite direction of the second parallax radiograph, confirming it is on the external aspect of the lingual/palatal or buccal root respectively. In multirooted teeth, the IRR lesion in one root canal may be superimposed onto another unaffected root canal, thus causing confusion or even misdiagnosed as an ECR lesion. Several studies have confirmed that CBCT improves the diagnosis and treatment planning of root resorption when compared to radiographs.

Management

The management of inflammatory and replacement IRR are similar, it is essential to assess the extent of hard tissue destruction by taking a CBCT scan. If a perforation is detected, then irrigation must be limited to the coronal extent of the IRR to prevent an inadvertent hypochlorite accident. In advanced perforated cases, a combined nonsurgical/surgical may be warranted.

Endodontic treatment should be considered only if the tooth appears to be restorable. The main objective of the treatment is to remove the bacteria and disinfect the root canal system, at the same time eliminating any remaining apical vital tissue, which is sustaining the resorption. Profuse bleeding may occur due to the granulomatous nature being disturbed and will stop once the inflamed pulpal tissue and granulation tissue have been completely removed.

The canal should still be negotiable in cases of moderate Internal replacement root resorption; however, in more advanced cases, fine ultrasonic tips may be necessary to fragment the metaplastic bone-like deposits to allow patency of the root canal to be established.

Sodium hypochlorite is the irrigant of choice, due to the irregular nature of the resorptive defect, the irrigant should be energized after which an intracanal calcium hydroxide medicament may be used to enhance the disinfection and dissolve pulp tissue remnants in the inaccessible parts of the root canal space, i.e. the resorptive defect.

Thermoplasticized canal filling techniques are indicated to improve the sealing of the irregular IRR defect. Warm vertical compaction has been shown to be a more effective root canal filling technique compared to lateral condensation and carrier-based techniques. If the resorption defect has perforated the root canal wall, bioactive hydraulic silicate cements [i.e. mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), Biodentine] should be used to repair the perforation.

In cases where the perforating IRR defects are not amenable for internal repair, a surgical approach is indicated. The root canal system should first be accessed prior to the surgical repair and occluded with well-fitting GP points to maintain the patency of root canals from unintentional blockage in the subsequent surgical repair. Surgical exposure and debridement of the perforation followed by repair using MTA are recommended. The root canal system can then be disinfected, instrumented and filled with thermo plasticized GP or with a hybrid of GP and bioactive materials.

Extraction is indicated in cases where IRR is too extensive to be managed effectively. These compromised teeth are likely to fracture when they are extracted as they have been weakened by the IRR, and therefore, the patient should be consented for a surgical extraction.

Recently, regenerative endodontic procedures (REP) have been used to treat perforating IRR. However, more clinical studies are required to investigate the exact healing mechanism and to allow for a more standardized treatment protocol to improve the reproducibility of the result. Besides, tooth discolouration after REP should also be considered especially in anterior teeth, which are aesthetically demanding.

External Root Resorption

External Surface Resorption

External surface resorption (ESR) is pressure-induced resorption and occurs on the external surface of the root, it is noninfective and self-limiting, i.e. once the source of the pressure has been eliminated, cemental repair ensues and it has also been described as pressure resorption.

Clinical Features

Surface resorption is usually asymptomatic and diagnosed as an incidental radiographic finding. The clinical findings are usually unremarkable, with no signs of endodontic disease. The affected teeth respond normally to pulp sensitivity tests.

Radiographic Features

Asymmetric loss of external root surface adjacent to the source of pressure from an impacted tooth, cyst or tumour is a common radiographic presentation. In advanced cases, this may result in perforation of the root canal. Surface resorption associated with orthodontic treatment may cause flattening or blunting of the root apices resulting in the affected teeth appearing to be shorter than neighbouring teeth, which have not been subjected to high orthodontic forces. The use of CBCT has resulted in increased detection and more accurate determination of the extent and nature of surface resorption.

Management

ESR is managed by the appropriate elimination of the aetiological factor, i.e. excessive pressure, for example, removal of an impacted tooth or management of a cyst.

A temporary pause of 3 months in active orthodontic treatment has been suggested to allow the resorbed cementum to heal in the case of surface resorption associated with orthodontic treatment. Termination of orthodontic treatment may be indicated when there is significant ESR. It has been reported that the ESR diagnosed after 6 to 12 months of orthodontic treatment with fixed appliances stabilizes resulting in minimal further ESR postorthodontic treatment.

To be continued.....